

Transferable Skills – Report 3

Deliverable 2.8

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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 2.8. Transferable Skills – Report 3

Version 1

Author:

Lorraine Farrelly (UREAD)

Version	Date	Authors
0.1	05.11.23	Lorraine Farrelly (UREAD)
0.2	17.11.2023	Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL)
0.3	15.12.2023	Stephen Gage (UREAD)
1	20.12.2023	Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL)

Table of contents

Executive summary.....	5
1. Introduction.....	6
2. Course aims	7
3. Learning outcomes	7
4. Course structure	7
5. Learning activities	10
5.1. Session 1: Tools for communication (17.3.23).....	10
5.2. Independent work (18.3.23-3.7.23).....	13
5.3. Session 2: Hands-on Workshop.....	13
5.4. Session 3: Lecture and Workshop (15.5.23).....	13
5.5. Session 4: Lecture and Hands-on Workshop (3.7.23) (Reading Summer School)	16
5.6. Session 5: Task 1 and 2 Presentations (4.9.23).....	17
6. Resources.....	17
7. Outputs	17
8. Course evaluation.....	18
Annex 1– Tasks feedback	1
Annex 2– Evaluation survey	2

Executive summary

This document describes the content and implementation process of the Transferable Skills 3 course “Communication and dissemination; Engagement and impact” (TS3), conducted from March to October 2023 . It presents the course aims, learning outcomes, structure and content, learning activities, resources, and outputs. The purpose of the course is to provide ESRs with the basic skills to carry out effective communication and dissemination of their research work in different contexts (community, professional, research) and to engage with different stakeholders.

Transferable skills covered under TS3 include three topics: (a) communication and dissemination of research (b) engagement and impact and (c) post-occupancy evaluation. TS3 is a 4-ECTS course, which equates to approximately 100 hours of learning, including online and in-person sessions and self-directed work.

The document also presents the results of the course evaluation in three settings: at the Zagreb Workshop 3, at the Reading Summer School 3, and overall. The Annexes include the feedback from ESRs, and the final survey results for TS3.

1. Introduction

This report aims to comprehensively document the implementation process of the course Transferable Skills 3 “Communication and dissemination; Engagement and impact” (TS3). It includes course aims, learning outcomes, structure and content, learning activities, resources, and outputs. TS3 is the third of three transferable skills modules which jointly aim to foster personal qualities, entrepreneurship and professional career and communication, engagement and impact. The course covered two parts which are guided by the UK Research Development Framework¹:

- Communication and Dissemination: Communication methods, communication media, publication.
- Engagement and Impact: Teaching, public engagement, enterprise, policy, society and culture, global citizenship.

TS3 is designed to equip early-stage researchers (ESRs) with basic skills for effective communication and dissemination of their research across various contexts – community, professional and research settings. The course specifically targets enhancing ESRs’ understanding of research engagement and impact, while introducing approaches to post-occupancy evaluation.

The course was prepared with input from the ESRs. The contents and tasks were discussed with them prior to the sessions so they could provide feedback about how this would support their research development effectively.

RMT3 ran in parallel to TS3. The learning activities in both courses shared the common goal of seamlessly integrating tasks with the ongoing PhD research projects, secondments, and the work carried out at WP4 “Transdisciplinary affordable and sustainable housing research framework.” The design of tasks and assignments aimed to enhance this interconnectivity, optimizing the efforts and time of researchers (Figure 1).

¹ <https://www.vitae.ac.uk/researchers-professional-development/about-the-vitae-researcher-development-framework>

Figure 1. Connections between RMT3/TS3 courses with individual and collaborative research

2. Course aims

TS3 has the following learning aims:

- To develop ESRs' skills and knowledge of communication and dissemination of their research
- To develop ESRs' skills in research conduct and self-management
- To enhance ESRs' skills to evaluate the built environment through aspects of post-occupancy evaluation

3. Learning outcomes

On the successful completion of the TS3 module, the ESRs were expected to demonstrate the following outcomes:

- Ability to communicate and disseminate their research
- Ability to develop approaches to measure engagement and impact of their research on a range of stakeholders
- Understanding of the value of post-occupancy evaluation and ways to undertake it

4. Course structure

Figure 2 shows the timeline for the TS3 course running from March to September 2023. The course was integrated with other network activities, and some of the sessions of RMT3 course ran in parallel to TS3.

Figure 2. TS3 course structure as integrated with the network activities

Responding to feedback from previous TS courses, ESRs engaged in preliminary discussions regarding the proposed content of the course, providing ample opportunities for open discussion.

The course was delivered in a blended learning format; a combination of asynchronous and synchronous (on-line and in-person) learning opportunities. This included online lectures, seminars and workshops.

There were in-person sessions during the workshop at Zagreb (March 2023) and the summer school at Reading (July 2023) which was an opportunity for discussion and feedback on draft task submissions.

This course delivery was coordinated with colleagues leading RMT3 to ensure there was some coordination around content, delivery times and workload for the ESRs.

Table 1 provides an overview of the programme structure with dates (March-September 2023) and time slots, session titles, brief content descriptions as well as the lead RE-DWELL staff. Further information is provided in Section 5 Learning activities.

Table 1. TS3 session briefs

Sessions	Activities	Facilitators
Before 17.3.23 Online	INDEPENDENT WORK Preparation for SESSION 1; complete reading tasks on interpreting scientific claims and communicating your research.	ESRs
17.3.23 Online	SESSION 1: Lecture and discussion Tools for communication	Caroline Knowles Lorraine Farrelly
18.3.23–3.7.23 Online	INDEPENDENT WORK Task 1: Communication Plan for research Task 2: Impact Plan for research	ESRs
30.3.23 Workshop 3	SESSION 2: Hands-on workshop Using communication techniques to inform research communication Joint session with RMT3 at Zagreb workshop	Adrienne Csizmady Lorraine Farrelly
15.5.23 Online	SESSION 3: Lecture and workshop Engagement and Impact: approaches and opportunities Preparing a communication and impact plan	Calum Kirk Lorraine Farrelly
3.7.23 Summer School 3	SESSION 4: Lecture and hands-on workshop Lecture: Post Occupancy Evaluation: Communication and processes Workshop: Discussion of Draft Impact plan and Communication Plan	Gloria Vargas Lisa Lazareck-Asunta
4.9.23 Online	SESSION 5: Task 1 and 2 Presentations Individual presentation of outcomes of Tasks 1 and 2	ESRs Lorraine Farrelly

TS3 is worth 4 ECTS, approximately 100 hours of learning, including online and in-person sessions and self-directed work (Table 2).

Table 2. Learning by type of activity, event and ECTS (1 ECTS= 25 hours)

Events	Course	Workshop 3	Summer School 3
	50 hours (2 ECTS)	25 hours (1 ECTS)	25 hours (1 ECTS)
Online lectures	4	-	-
Online seminars	4	-	-
F2F lectures	-	2	-
F2F workshops	-	2	1
Presentations	2	-	2
Hybrid Panel session	-	-	2
Tutorials	-	-	1
Independent learning (80%)	40	21	19
Total hours	50	25	25

There were four main learning components in TS3:

- On-line lectures
- On-line seminars
- In-person lectures SS3

These course materials, including recordings, are available in MS Teams:

- Course descriptions
- Recorded Lectures
- Resources
- Sessions
- Tasks

5. Learning activities

Specifically, TS3 training and learning activities were as follows:

5.1. Session 1: Tools for communication (17.3.23)

The first part of the course consisted of online lectures delivered using Teams. This lecture covered:

- Why communicate?
- Examples of how academics use different channels
- How to plan communications (Audience, Channel, Timing, Message, Engagement) – very quick overview

- Understanding your audience – taking ‘policymakers’ as an audience
- Developing clear messages / some tips on writing
- How to write a policy brief
- Initial ideas for a research communication plan

Learning aims

- To develop ESRs’ skills and knowledge of communication and dissemination of their research

Learning outcomes

- Ability to communicate and disseminate their research.
- Ability to develop approaches to measure engagement and impact of their research on a range of stakeholders.

The session was a presentation by Caroline Knowles from the University of Reading, an expert in communication of research, methods and techniques to communicate effectively. The session also included a Q and A with ESRs (Figures 3-4).

Figure 3. TS3 presentation on communication tools

University of Reading

5) UNDERSTANDING POLICYMAKERS' NEEDS

WORLDVIEWS	
Researchers tend to	Policymakers tend to
Question the fundamentals of policy approaches and thus are often radical in their proposals	Have a programme management and political view of public policy and are resistant to changes
Be idealistic or not see the constraints of management and delivery of everyday government services	Be driven primarily by budget and capacity restrictions, political will, and election/budgetary cycles
Talk in academic concepts and jargon	Talk in terms of bureaucracy, budgets and politics
Be motivated by publication, funding and donor agendas, recognition and new research commissions	Be motivated by doing what works and what fits

- Policymakers are experts – and are advised by experts
- They will say: "Don't bring me a problem, bring me a solution"
- Recommendations may change over time (e.g. as governments change – or as new evidence emerges)

31

Figure 4. TS3 topic: Understanding policymakers needs

Based on the presentation and discussion, Task 1 was to prepare a brief for a Communication Plan of their research, following this template (Table 3):

Table 3. Task 1: Communication Plan Template

Page 1	<p>Title: Make it as simple and direct as possible. Don't try and be too clever. Summary: Up to 150 words (max). This needs to capture the main ideas of your</p> <p>Brief in a clear and direct way and catch the reader's attention.</p> <p>Picture: A good clear photo with a pithy caption relevant to your message.</p> <p>Overview: Up to 200 words, that will draw the reader into the subject, raising some key questions that will make your reader want to turn the page</p> <p>Key Points or Facts and Figures box</p>
Pages 2 – 3	<p>Communication Plan: Total of up to 800 words developing the main evidence/arguments</p> <p>Include figures, charts or diagrams if appropriate to help make your Brief more eye-catching and appealing (but make sure they are clear and easy for non- specialists to read/use). Or use one or two text boxes giving examples or a case study (100-150 words each).</p>
Page 4	<p>Policy implications: Up to 300 words wrapping up your Brief and tackling the "so what?" question. Make recommendations for practical actions that could be taken.</p> <p>References and further reading: Up to 4 key references giving a broad representation of research on the topic and links to key information sources. This could be a mixture of your own most relevant paper and other sources.</p> <p>Acknowledgements and credits: Keep it short, e.g. This Policy Brief was written by xx, based on a longer research paper 'Title'. Don't forget to include acknowledgement of your funder and research partners if appropriate (you can send the Brief to them to help disseminate).</p> <p>Date (month and year) and your Contact details, including website for further info.</p>

5.2. Independent work (18.3.23-3.7.23)

Based on the skills acquired in Session 1, ESRs were asked to work on developing a draft Communication Plan (Task 1). In addition, based on the skills acquired in Session 3, ESRs were asked to develop an Impact Plan (Task 2). Drafts of these tasks were presented at the Summer School 3 in Reading, July 2023, where feedback was provided.

5.3. Session 2: Hands-on Workshop

As part of the Zagreb workshop in March 2023, there were two collaborative sessions between the RMT3 and TS3 courses, co-organized by Adrienne Csizmady (RMT3) and Lorraine Farrelly (TS3) (Figure 5). The objective of this activity was to assist ESRs in determining the most effective methods for disseminating their findings to non-academic stakeholders. Working in teams, ESRs identified and mapped target groups/non-academic actors, methods, and communication tools. The goal was to understand their connections to the three core RE-DWELL research areas: Design, planning, and building; Community participation; and Policy and financing.

Figure 5. TS3 discussions in Zagreb workshops

During the discussions ESR talked about their approaches to communicating their research to a range of audiences.

5.4. Session 3: Lecture and Workshop (15.5.23)

The online presentation was delivered by Dr Calum Kirk, impact development manager, and Lorraine Farrelly, both from the University of Reading via Teams (Figures 6, 7). The topic was impact planning for research. Students were presented with some examples and case studies to illustrate what an impact plan looks like. Then the process of developing an impact plan was described.

There was a discussion session that all ESRs contributed to. A scenario was used to ask questions about how an impact plan or problem statement could be developed from this scenario. Then a series of questions were discussed which could be used to create an impact plan for each student. This included how to frame a research question and from this how to develop an impact plan and who the relevant audience may be for this research.

Learning aims

- To develop ESRs' skills and knowledge of communication and dissemination of their research

Learning outcomes

- Ability to develop approaches to measure engagement and impact of their research on a range of stakeholders

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Figure 6. TS3 Session 3 lecture

DISCUSSION TIME!

- All discuss and come up with a possible problem statement for an example research project
- Problem: Approached by a local housing authority to develop a vacant plot of land due to the original developer pulling out
 - What level of the problem are you addressing?
 - Who are the beneficiaries of the research?
 - Who might be in a position to help?
 - What might change look like?
 - What are some examples of engaged research?

Figure 7. TS3 discussion time with ESRs as part of the session

Based on the presentation and discussion, Task 2 was to prepare a brief for an Impact Plan of their research, following a template (Table 4). This series of questions was developed to support ESRs to prepare their impact plan or problem statement of their research, to list the contributions their research has made to impact in their area, and to identify potential areas of engaged research. This table can then be used to develop an impact plan.

Table 4. Task 2: Impact plan template

1. Describe your research in no more than 3 sentences.
2. Identify specific beneficiaries/external stakeholders/partners who may be interested in your research:
3. What real world problems are these beneficiaries/external stakeholders/partners facing that your research could help to solve?
4. Identify how your research contributes towards impact. What will change look like?
5. What potential avenues of engaged research would be appropriate for your research?:

5.5. Session 4: Lecture and Hands-on Workshop (3.7.23) (Reading Summer School)

The presentation was delivered by Dr Gloria Vargas, researcher at the University of Reading and PTE Architects.

Learning aims

- To enhance ESRs' skills to evaluate the built environment through aspects of post-occupancy evaluation.
 - a. Post Occupancy Evaluation: to present the ideas tools and techniques
 - b. To present a set of case studies of Post occupancy evaluation
 - c. To discuss possibilities for POE in ESR's work

Learning outcomes

- Understanding of the value of post-occupancy evaluation and ways to undertake it.
 - a. Ability to identify projects that could respond to POE
 - b. Ability to undertake POE
 - c. Knowledge of relevance of POE to research

The presentation consisted of an hour and 30 minute lecture and 30 minutes Q and A and discussion (Figure 8). Vargas shared her experience with Post-Occupancy Evaluation (POE). Originally focused on assessing how well a building is functioning, POE has evolved to encompass social value, emotions, people's perceptions, and experiences. She highlighted the expanded scope of POE, noting its potential to assist architects in offering improved services to clients, addressing performance gaps at both the building and social levels, and providing evidence-based data.

Figure 8. TS3 Presentation on 03.07.23

The presentation was followed by a workshop session. It was an opportunity for all the ESRs to share their draft communication plan (Task 1) and impact plan (Task 2) to demonstrate their response to the Tasks for the course. A member of the Impact planning team from the University of Reading, Dr Lisa Lazareck-Asunta was available to provide feedback.

5.6. Session 5: Task 1 and 2 Presentations (4.9.23)

This online session was coordinated by Lorraine Farrelly and attended by all ESRs. In the online presentation session all ESRs presented their plans and there was a discussion and feedback from all the group. Task 1 was a Communication Plan, based on the 4-page template provided (see Figure 6). Task 2 was an Impact Plan, based on the 2-page template provided (see Figure 10).

During the discussion, many key points emerged. Audiences that might be interested in the ESR topics of research include local government authorities, housing policymakers and planners, and, of course, the housing cooperatives, the community organisations and housing advocacy groups. There is potential of the preparation of the impact and communication plan to inform ESR's plan about what they many want to do next in terms of career steps. Once there is clear idea of the impact each ERS identifies, it can be effective to create focus groups to consider dissemination to key groups the research may impact. This might include ESR's going back to contacts made during the research to help ensure impact.

6. Resources

Learning was facilitated by the resources provided by the lectures and literature recommendations used throughout the different tasks.

The learning materials were available in Teams. They included templates to carry out a communication plan and an impact plan.

The folder structure was the following:

- Course description
- Sessions
- Submissions

Online lectures were recorded and available for later use in Teams.

7. Outputs

As described in Section 5, ESRs were to do two tasks which led to the following outputs:

Task 1: Communication Plan

ESR's were required to prepare a communication plan to propose how they will communicate their research to a range of identified stakeholders.

Task 2: Impact Plan

ESRs were required to an impact plan to describe the potential impact of their research on a range of stake holders and on a range of policies relevant to their research.

Supervisors' feedback on these two tasks is presented in the annexes.

8. Course evaluation

ESRs evaluated the TS3 course in three contexts: in the Workshop in Zagreb, in the Summer School in Reading, and the evaluation of the course as a whole. The highlights of each evaluation are presented next; Annex 3-Evaluation surveys contains the full evaluation results for TS3.

Workshop 3 (Zagreb):

The workshop was evaluated by 20 participants through an anonymous online survey. The aim was to evaluate their experience attending the workshop and to identify areas needing improvement. The online survey was completed by 12 ESRs and 8 supervisors/co-supervisors. It included question about the TS3 session (Table 5).

Table 5. Survey results for Workshop 3

Questions	Answers	Supervisors / Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
Please evaluate "TS3 hands on session, Lorraine Farrelly" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	19	4,43	3,83	4,05

Some positive feedback included:

"Helpful exercise."

"It brought up interesting discussions among the group members. For me I discovered new stakeholders that my research would be useful for them to be aware of."

"It was a necessary activity to link what we had previously discussed in our groups with the rest of the ESRs. Hopefully, this can result in a compilation of stakeholders from all organisations and institutions across Europe. This could be a valuable resource for all of us in the future. And proof that new channels of communication and communities of practise have emerged with the implementation of the project."

It was also suggested:

"The session was useful. However, we had already prepared material for the Stage 1 of the task which was not presented at all. It is a bit of a pity that we have to re-write and re-organise information. Maybe a good practice for the future (especially when we are requested to work in Miro) would be to be given the board/template in advance and been asked to work on this."

Summer School 3 (Reading):

The workshop was evaluated by 18 participants through an anonymous online survey. The aim was to evaluate their experience attending the workshop and to identify areas needing improvement. The online survey was completed by 8 ESRs and 9 supervisors/co-supervisors (and 1 partner organisation).

Two sessions related to TS3 (Table 6):

Table 6. Survey results for Summer School 3

Questions	Answers	Supervisors / Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
"Tools and methods of POE" session	13	4,5	4,1	4,3
"Workshop - Reflect on Assignments" session	10	4,3	4,1	4,2

Some positive comments:

"Very grateful that Dr Gloria Vargas shared all those insights on POE with practical and operational toolboxes. Her work is inspiring for the development of our own methodological approaches."

"The session was very helpful and fun. Lisa and Lorraine were excellent facilitators, helping us frame our research through very targeted questions, keeping a very nice energy during the session despite the long day."

However, one ESR noted a lack of time:

"It was interesting to present our reflections [...] but due to the lack of time there was no possibility for comments on our work, which would have been very useful."

Overall course evaluation:

TS3 was evaluated by 11 ESRs through an anonymous online survey (Table 7). All comments are included in Annex 3.

Table 7. Survey result for the course

Questions	Answers	Average
Please evaluate Transferrable Skills TS3 session.	11	3,8
How would you rate the overall organization of the online and face-to-face activities of the TS3 course?	11	4,0
Session 1 (March 17, 2023)	11	4,1
Session 2 (March 30, 2023)	10	3,6
Session 3 (May 15, 2023)	11	4,0
Session 4 (July 3-4, 2023)	11	3,9
Session 5 (September 4, 2023)	11	3,6
Communication and dissemination	11	3,8
Engagement and impact	11	3,9

Ability to engage with external stakeholders (non-academic sectors, local administrations, civic organizations), dealing with sustainable and affordable housing	11	3,5
Knowledge of communication and dissemination mechanisms of own research	11	3,5
Understanding the value of research outputs, sharing and impact	11	3,9
Post occupancy evaluation and Awareness of post occupancy evaluation in housing	11	3,7
Communication and dissemination	11	3,8
Engagement and impact	11	3,9

Annex 1– Tasks feedback

RE-DWELL TS3 course Tasks feedback

ESRs were required to produce a research communication and impact plan of their research

A sample of discussion points provided to ESRs is given below.

Table 1.1. Feedback to Tasks 1 and 2

Category	Comments
Communication Plan	Consider how do you communicate to these different stakeholders that you have something worth saying in your research.
	Who are the main organisations that you think you need to get your message to in terms of stakeholders for example local government, social housing providers, there's mortgage companies, funders. Who are the main organisations that you need to communicate.
	Consider to approach some of these people you've been interviewing through research as there are already relationships with these groups- build a communication plan with these organisations.
	Consider a communication plan to ensure that all of the research work is disseminated beyond your own context to other related contexts.
Impact Plan	How do you promote your research to the relevant organisations so you can get the impact that you want.
	Potential to impact design guidelines, building codes also associated groups such as housing providers and also contractors.
	Publications and papers can reach the audience of those influencers, those people who make decisions, which can have impact, which is why publications are so important.
	To inform policy or influence policy, it's really important to collaborate with people that have influenced and develop a professional inter disciplinary network.

Annex 2– Evaluation survey

This annex contains the questions and answers to the evaluation survey.

Please evaluate the organization, content and learning outcomes of the TS3 course. The purpose of this evaluation is to know what worked well and what needs to be changed in the next edition of the courses.

Please evaluate Transferrable Skills TS3

Comments:

- It was a good course overall, with good sessions, good activities and good speakers.
- It was a very practical course.
- Some of the lectures were very inspirational and I found really interesting to collaborate with my colleagues that were from other research areas.
- The ability to clearly articulate the value of our research is critical to achieving impact. This module helped me to organise and map the stakeholders who might be interested in my findings and establish the best ways to reach out to them.
- Lorraine listened to our suggestions and all sessions presented amazing content to learn from.

How would you rate the overall organization of the online and face-to-face activities of the TS3 course?

Comments:

- Nice organisation and complementarity to RMT3.
- Well-organised and delivered.

Session 1 (March 17, 2023)

Comments:

- Very informative overview on communication methods.
- Although many of the concepts taught in this lecture we already knew, it was great to have them as a reminder, to help us shape a communication strategy and have greater impact.
- It is relevant to the current phase of the project. We all need to think about who and how we communicate RE-DWELL outputs.
- One of the best presentations. Caroline is experienced, and I learn a lot from her. Her presentation was straight to the point.

Session 2 (March 30, 2023)

Comments:

- Great conversations. It would be nice if supervisors participated in a similar exercise to share their experiences and make the sessions more informative for us too.
- Unfortunately I was not able to attend the Zagreb workshop.
- The workshop was very well organised. The space was adequate to foster discussion.

Session 3 (May 15, 2023)Comments:

- This was a new skill for many of us, so the session was very informative.
- I found the lecture by Calum very interesting as well. It helped me understand other ways to have impact through our research other than in the academic world, for example by collaborating with companies that are leading change and are impactful. That is why for our research is important to identify what is the need in the real world in order to address that problem. Another important outcome from this lecture was the importance of showing evidence to have impact, of being able to demonstrate through indicators and have a good narrative to articulate it.
- The communication and impact plan is a very useful document. It helped me clarify the key aspects of my research.
- Very practical advice.

Session 4 (July 3-4, 2023)Comments:

- Great method nicely presented, yet being quite specific makes it not very useful for everyone. Overall I am happy to have heard about this.
- Very relevant and well-delivered. The guest speakers showed us good examples of how these activities are conducted between academia and industry.

Session 5 (September 4, 2023)Comments:

- The tasks felt a bit forced and unnecessary
- The tasks were a good exercise to incentivise us to apply the knowledge learned into our own research. But due to insufficient time we could not receive comments on the work done. As I mentioned it would have been beneficial to have a one-to-one session to discuss this or that our supervisor would as well attend the lectures to give us more support on this topic.
- It was interesting to hear from my colleagues. However, as is so often the case, there was not enough time to cover all the projects in the same depth.
- It was so cool to see myself writing a policy brief. It felt phenomenal to get in that mood and get ready to next chapters of our life!

Please explain which sessions best met your expectations and whyComments:

- Every aspect of this course was designed to the benefit of the ESR, I have learned a good deal of skills, particularly PEO, policy briefing and dissemination plans and activities.
- Session 3 because it was very practical.
- The session by Calum best met my expectations as it made me rethink some of the aspects of my research in order to make it significant for the real-world challenges.
- All the sessions related to creating an impact plan and drafting a policy brief were highly insightful.
- Session One with Caroline Knowles from The University of Reading.

Please explain in which ways has the TS3 course contributed to the development of your research?Comments:

- It has helped my better understanding of communication methods and impact plans.
- I think that TS3 is a course with a great potential and there is a lot of knowledge compressed into these lectures. It has contributed very positively in the development of my research especially in understanding how to measure impact, the different ways to achieve it, how to shape the narrative depending on the audience or what levels of influence and of interest do each of the audiences have.
- It helped me clarify and better communicate key aspects of my project.
- It gave me more confidence and inspired me to think of how I can communicate my research to different stakeholders and how can it benefit supporting policy makers. I loved the advice to not use Jargons! because as a non-native English speaker it annoys me. So knowing that it is a good thing to not use jargons was good news and made complete sense to be precise and simple to transfer our key messages.

Communication and disseminationComments:

- I think that the theory is very clear, I just need to take time to apply it in practice. Dissemination is not always one of the top priorities when there are so many other things to do, but it is definitely necessary to spend time to communicate the findings.
- The exercises were very useful to understand the importance of clearly stating the value of your research to non-academic stakeholders.

Engagement and impactComments:

- The module allowed me to realise the impact of engagement tools and channels in the dissemination of outputs.

Ability to engage with external stakeholders (non-academic sectors, local administrations, civic organizations), dealing with sustainable and affordable housingComments:

- The exercises were very useful to understand the importance of clearly stating the value of your research to non-academic stakeholders.
- I wish we had more training in this and practice.

Knowledge of communication and dissemination mechanisms of own researchComments:

- I must say that the particular application to each of our own research was lacking a little bit. When doing our individual presentations there was not enough time for feedback therefore It would have been beneficial to have individual tutoring sessions to discuss about this.
- The module allowed me to realise the impact of engagement tools and channels in the dissemination of outputs.

Understanding the value of research outputs, sharing and impact

Comments:

- The module allowed me to realise the impact of engagement tools and channels in the dissemination of outputs. I have started to be more active on those platforms.

Post occupancy evaluation and Awareness of post occupancy evaluation in housing Communication and dissemination

Comments:

- It was interesting. It highlights the importance of engaging with ALL the housing actors.

What aspects of the TS3 course could be enhanced to support the objectives?

Comments:

- It was well organised.

- More tailor-made learning opportunities.

- The assignments felt unnecessary.

- As said before, after we created our first communication plan it would have been good to have a tutoring session either with one of the lecturers, with the responsible of the work package or with our supervisor about this assignment. Once we would receive the feedback, we would then improve the communication plan and present it to our peers. I realised that presentations amongst 3 people work much better as there is more time to discuss and share insights, people don't get overwhelmed/tired with so many presentations, and a more casual scenario gives rise to a greater involvement of all peers.

- I think the course was well organised and the activities were a good complement to the presentations and discussions we had during the course. So I think it achieved its objectives.